

TRANSLATING ENGLISH IDIOMS INTO UZBEK: CHALLENGES ILLUSTRATED BY O.WILDE'S "THE PICTURE OF DORIAN GRAY"

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Abstract: *This article first analyzes the concept of idioms and aphorisms and their role in language and culture. It also examines the central ideas of Oscar Wilde's works, specifically the philosophical and aesthetic concepts in *The Picture of Dorian Gray*, as well as the idioms and aphorisms found in the novel through practical examples. Furthermore, it investigates the challenges that arise when translating these English expressions into Uzbek.*

Keywords: *idiom, aphorism, translation difficulties, idiomatic expression, translation strategies, translation through equivalence, translation by meaning, descriptive translation, literal translation, Oscar Wilde, *The Picture of Dorian Gray*, linguistic and cultural context, artistic and philosophical value.*

Introduction: Idioms and aphorisms are important units that reflect the national and cultural richness of a language. They not only enhance the artistic beauty of the language but also convey the worldview, values, and life experience of the people. The main idea of Oscar Wilde's works is manifested not only in his unique style but also in his sharp critical perspective on the society of his time. In his works, he places beauty, art, and individuality above all else. Several key ideas lie at the core of his works. First, he promoted the principle "art for art's sake," opposing the idea of linking art to moral or social purposes. According to him, the main function of art is to create beauty and provide pleasure. The second important idea is the conflict between outward beauty and inner corruption. In "*The Picture of Dorian Gray*", the protagonist's appearance remains unchanged while his sins and moral decay are reflected in his portrait, symbolizing the contrast between external and internal worlds. Furthermore, Wilde satirizes Victorian society, criticizing false morality, hypocrisy, and rigid rules, which is evident in comedies such as "*The Importance of Being Earnest*". Another central idea is individuality and self-expression. Wilde believed that every person has the right to express

themselves freely beyond societal norms. This article aims to analyze the idioms and aphorisms in Wilde's "The Picture of Dorian Gray" and highlight the challenges of translating them into Uzbek.

MAIN PART:

1. The Concept of Idioms and Aphorisms. An idiom, idiomatic unit, or phraseme is a combination of two or more words that are semantically interconnected and used as a whole, non-divisible, fixed expression. Unlike syntactic structures that are formed by freely selecting and combining words in speech, idioms are used as pre-formed lexical and grammatical units; no part of an idiom can be omitted or altered. Examples include: *anqovning urug'i, arpasini xom urmoq, chuchvarani xom sanamoq, terisiga sig'may ketmoq, kapalagi uchmoq, kungli joyiga tushmoq, qo'li ochiq, qulog'i og'ir*, and others. Their meanings are revealed in specific speech contexts according to historical usage norms. An aphorism (from Greek ἀφορισμός: aphorismos, denoting 'delimitation', 'distinction', and 'definition') is a concise, terse, laconic, or memorable expression of a general truth or principle. Aphorisms are often passed down through generations. They are generally distinct from adages, brocards, chiasmus, epigrams, maxims (legal or philosophical), principles, proverbs, and sayings, although some may be considered types of aphorisms. Aphorisms usually require interpretation to be fully understood. In *A Theory of the Aphorism*, Andrew Hui defined an aphorism as "a short saying that requires interpretation."

2. Main Strategies for Translating Idiomatic Expressions. When translating idiomatic expressions, it is essential to consider both the literal meaning and the cultural or figurative nuances embedded in the original language. Different strategies can be applied depending on whether a direct equivalent exists in the target language or whether the idiom carries culturally specific connotations.

- 1. Translation through equivalence** – If a stable expression exists in the target language, using an equivalent is the most effective method. For example, the English idiom "to kill two birds with one stone" has an Uzbek equivalent: *bir o'q bilan ikki quyonni urmoq*.
- 2. Translation by meaning** – When no exact equivalent exists, the meaning is conveyed using a simple sentence in the target language. For instance, "to burn the midnight oil" is translated as *kechasi bilan ishlamoq* (to work late at night).
- 3. Descriptive translation** – Explaining the idiom's meaning with a broader sentence, often used for culturally specific expressions. For example, "Achilles' heel" is rendered as *insonning zaif tomoni, kuchsiz*

nuqtasi (a person's weak point). 4. **Literal translation** – The least effective method, since the figurative meaning of idioms is lost. For instance, “to kick the bucket” literally translates as *chelakni tepmoq*, but its actual meaning is “to die.”

3. Analysis of Idioms in the Work. In Wilde's “*The Picture of Dorian Gray*”, many idioms and aphorisms appear, serving as a key tool for expressing the author's aesthetic views and critical stance on human nature and society. For example, the phrase “The face tells a story” is literally translated as “*Yuz bir hikoya aytadi*”; its meaning is “One can infer a person's life and character from their facial expressions.” The Uzbek equivalent “*Yuzdan hamma narsa bilinadi*” fully preserves its figurative meaning, making equivalence the most effective translation strategy. Another example is “The mirror of the soul,” literally translated as “*ruhning oynasi*”, meaning a person's inner world, especially the heart, reflected in their appearance. The Uzbek equivalent is “*Ko'z qalb oynasi*”. The phrase “to sell one's soul” means sacrificing human values for wealth, interest, or power. The Uzbek equivalent is “*Jonini sotmoq*”, which carries religious and moral connotations. Thus, the meaning is preserved in translation.

4. Challenges in the Translation Process. Wilde's aphorisms and idioms carry strong cultural and philosophical connotations. Literal translation may reduce the artistic and philosophical value of the work. Therefore, the translator must creatively find solutions to preserve both the meaning and the figurative expression of idioms and aphorisms.

Conclusion: The study examined the concept of idioms and aphorisms and their role in language and culture. It also analyzed the central ideas in Oscar Wilde's works, particularly the philosophical and aesthetic ideas in “*The Picture of Dorian Gray*”, along with idioms and aphorisms, using practical examples. The study highlights the challenges of translating idioms into Uzbek, showing that Wilde's idiomatic expressions and aphorisms carry not only linguistic but also cultural and artistic value. Therefore, translators should creatively render English metaphors into Uzbek using culturally appropriate equivalents.

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